

AN ANALYSIS OF ETHIOPIA-ERITREA RELATIONS: IMPLICATIONS ON THE PROTECTION OF REFUGEES

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Ethiopia-Eritrea relations and implications for protection of refugees. The study was guided by migrations system theory by Kritz and Zlotnik and the aim of this study is to analysis the factors that have made Eritrean migrate to Ethiopia and measures taken by the Ethiopian government to protect Eritrean refugees that have migrated to Ethiopia. The study adopted ex-post research design while data for this study was gotten through secondary source such as textbooks, journal articles, newspapers, magazines and internet. The findings of the study showed that there are several factors that have made Eritrean to migrate to Ethiopia which includes; Identity-based characteristics of the Eritrean population, discrimination towards minorities, state role in the marginalization of minorities, religious and gender issues. The failure to provide facilities and other livelihood support has a negative impact on refugees' that have made them not to be protected to the fullest. Based on the findings the study recommended among others: that Eritrea refugees in Ethiopia must be meaningfully included in consultations at national and international levels about frameworks and responses that will affect them, including plans for national-level and Ethiopia government must set up plans that prioritize not only the material needs of refugees but also more fundamental human needs to live a dignified life, to have the conditions enabling them to fulfill their aspirations, and the legal, social and psychological assistance needed to realize those.

Keywords: *Refugees, protection of refugees, discrimination, migration and conflict.*

INTRODUCTION

The 2008 tension on the Ethiopia-Eritrea border were as rigid as they have been since the parties signed the ceasefire that ended their 1998–2000 conflict. The peace process propelled by the Algiers Agreement has fizzled, yet there is not a single clear replacement or even framework for talks in sight. The Eritrea Ethiopia Border Commission (EEBC) shut its entryways without having delimited the border on the ground in November 2007; the United Nations Mission in Ethiopia and Eritrea (UNMEE) ended its mandate in August 2008; Eritrean troops re-occupied the Temporary Security Zone. Ethiopia remains in control of territories that the EEBC's demarcation put on the Eritrean side of the border, notably the emblematically significant town of Badme and Ethiopian and Eritrean troops are up close and personal along their highly militarized border. Eritrea is immovable in its position that the EEBC decision is final and has the sponsorship of global law. Ethiopia, thus, sticks to the influence it has by temperance of the accepted circumstance on the ground and its strong relations with the United States (US). The stalemate is both strong and costly. The Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Democratic Front (EPRDF), driven by Prime Minister Meles Zenawi, and the Eritrean People's Liberation Front (EPLF), driven by President Isaias Afwerki, collaborated closely to topple the fierce Mengistu Haile Mariam government in 1991. While the EPRDF united with different groups to form the Transitional Government of Ethiopia, the EPLF assumed control of Eritrea and built up a temporary government. In the month of April 1993 Eritreans casted a ballot overwhelmingly for independence in an UN-observed referendum. The EPRDF welcomed Eritrean independence and for quite a while the two nations and pioneers appeared to be ready to put past conflicts behind them and collaborate on a broad scope of political and economic issues. Be that as it may, by 1998 relations between the two nations had deteriorated. Disagreements between Addis Ababa and Asmara emerged over land-locked Ethiopia's entrance to Eritrean ports of Massawa and Asab, questions of how the new Eritrean money related to the current Ethiopian money and disagreements over the exact area of their poorly delineated border, in addition to other things. The exemplary objectives of state-and nation building drove the two regimes to present unlimited objectives and decline bargain on the indispensable issues of territoriality, legitimacy and identity. In May 1998, Eritrean military assaulted the contested border town of Badme, a utilization of military power that immediately amplified into full-scale war.

The historical connections and contentions between the two peoples, ruling parties and leaders made the savagery especially harsh. Meles and Isaias describe each other's conduct as a sellout, and the two nations share a political culture that values total triumph and zero-sum calculations over trade off and joint gains. This led both to be stiff-necked and made de-escalation difficult. The savagery created impressive setbacks and colossal expenses on the two sides. An estimated 70,000 to 100,000 individuals were executed, 1 million were dislodged, and a generation of development opportunities was wasted. After the time of military stalemate and inefficient negotiations, Ethiopia launched a noteworthy hostile in May 2000, broke through defences, and constrained Eritrea to pull its troops back to pre-May 1998 positions. Following a

June 2000 ceasefire understanding, the warring groups consented to a globally brokered agreement in Algiers in December 2000. A specially appointed group of states filled in as Witnesses to the agreements, including the Organization of African Unity (presently Africa Union), Algeria, the European Union (EU), and the US. The Algiers Agreement built up a ceasefire, created a 25-kilometer Temporary Security Zone (TSZ) to be watched by UNMEE and the EEBC to delimit the border, and a claims commission to survey liability for war damages. On the issue of the border, the agreement followed African practice and confirmed colonial borders. Under Article Four of the agreement, the EEBC was charged to delimit and outline the frontier settlement border dependent on appropriate colonial treaties (1900, 1902, and 1908) and relevant international law and this determination was final and authoritative. The commission unequivocally was not enabled to settle on choices *ex-aequo et bono*, that is, based on equity considerations. In spite of the fact that the ceasefire has held, the other core arrangements of the Algiers Agreement have not been executed and the general framework has fizzled. In April 2002, the EEBC issued its assurance and decided that the town of Badme was on the Eritrean side of the border while other, less symbolically significant territories claimed by Eritrea were on the Ethiopian side. The town of Badme was not the basic reason for the conflict, however the two regimes utilized it as the marker of whether it had ‘won’ or ‘lost’ the war, and consequently whether the awful sacrifices each made in the conflict were justified or futile. In this manner, the control of this little forlorn town ended up connected directly to the political fortunes even survival of the two regimes. Isaias, for instance, said that “hauling out of Badme might be compared to demanding that the sun won't rise in the first part of the day. It is unfathomable (Tronvoll, 1999). When the border decision was clear, Ethiopian leaders firmly questioned it and did everything short of resumption of threats to delay compliance. In a September 2003 letter to UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan, Prime Minister Meles dug in his heels and described the EEBC decision as absolutely illegal, uncalled for, and unreliable and required an elective mechanism to differentiate the boundary. This open denial of the EEBC represented a major test to the Algiers peace process and the guideline of a final and binding agreement. Meles later issued a five-point initiative of peace in November 2004 that declared acknowledgment of the border ruling on a fundamental level while at the same time calling for peace building discourse. As of late, Addis Ababa has expressed its unlimited acknowledgment of the decision yet its initial dismissal gives it little believability on the issue. Eritrea disappointed both by Ethiopia and by what it considered international pacification of Addis Ababa, took measures to compel the border demarcation issue in October 2005. Eritrea restricted UNMEE helicopter flights, which led the United Nations (UN) to pull back its forces from about half of its deployment sites.

In November 2005, the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) passed Resolution 1640, requesting that Eritrea lift its restrictions, Ethiopia acknowledge the EEBC’s border outline decisions, and the two nations turn around troop mobilization. The Resolution took steps to impose sanctions against Eritrea in the event that it didn’t remove the UNMEE restrictions. Tensions in late 2005 were high and an International Crisis Group report contended there were

disturbing signs that the commencement to renewed crisis may have started (International Crisis Group, 2005). The underlying US reaction to the crisis regarding UNMEE and the non-execution of Resolution 1640 was an improvised one-sided initiative to break the impasse. The US sent the Assistant Secretary of State for African Affairs, Jendayi Frazer, to the region where she met with Ethiopian officials, however was denied meetings in Asmara. A flurry of global meetings followed: Representatives of the Witnesses to the Algiers agreement met in New York in February 2006, and the EEBC met in London with officials from Addis Ababa and Asmara in March and May 2006; these meetings did not break the stalemate. In May 2006 the UNSC decreased the size of UNMEE's force from 3,300 to 2,300. In the wake of failing to unite Ethiopia and Eritrea for talks in June 2006, the EEBC concluded that: The circumstance is one which is beyond the Commission's powers to cure on the grounds of show implacability (Plaut, 2006). Ethiopia had moved from unyielding refusal to acknowledge the agreement to agreeing 'on a fundamental level and after that to tolerating without qualification (while requesting further talks). Eritrea would not acknowledge the requirement for extra negotiations and would not meet with UN representatives. As one observer commented, Ethiopia "is liable of throwing a tantrum" however Eritrea's "passive forceful" reaction has not helped (Pratt, 2006). The EEBC disbanded in November 2007, leaving the two parties maps with virtual division, yet without boundary pillars on the ground as called for in the Algiers Agreements. While the basic conflict was not constrained to the border issue, dividing the border was an important essential for advancement on other issues. In spite of these tensions, the stalemate stayed stable on the grounds that neither Asmara nor Addis Ababa had convincing motivations to break the ceasefire. Since international law underpins its position, Eritrea accepts that the global community should push Ethiopia to consent to the final and binding decision of EEBC. Ethiopia feels no need to modify the status qua since the agreement left it responsible of Badme and the international community has not put any significant pressure. The two regimes foresee the fast approaching breakdown of the other and accept that time is on its side. Tensions between the two states have been dislodged from the frozen border conflict into help for one another's resistance movements and proxy conflicts in Somalia. At the point when tensions increase, they will in general be displaced into surrogate conflicts instead of direct military confrontation on the border (Lyons, 2006).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This paper is intended to achieve two objectives which includes to; (1) examine the factors that have made Eritrean migrate to Ethiopia; and, (2) analysis measures taken by the Ethiopian government to protect Eritrean refugees that have migrated to Ethiopia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical review

The migration systems theory was adopted for this study, the theory gives a comprehensive view on the person's choice to migrate or not. This theory rose based on the critiques of preceding theories which did not sufficiently clarify why people move from one nation to the other,

however rather gave scraps of a heap of reasons. The proponents of this theory are Kritz and Zlotnik in 1992 and explained by others, for example, Castles and Miller (1998) is progressively utilized in comparative research. Accordingly, Castles and Miller (1998) observed that the theory accentuates international relations, political economy, collective action, and institutional variables. They are of the view that a migration system comprises two or more nations trading migrants with one another. The inclination is to analyze regional migration and how the people that migrate are been protected. This theory is concerned about looking at all the linkages between migration territories. Fawcett and Arnold (1987) characterized these linkages as the state-to-state relations and comparisons, mass culture connections and family and informal networks. Castles and Miller (1998) further talk about that this theory proposes that migratory movements happen from the existence of prior connections among sending and receiving nations based on colonization, political impact, trade, investment and cultural ties. They guarantee that this theory posits that any migratory movements is because of macro structures, for example, the political economy of the world market, interstate connections and laws collaborating with micro structures, for example, beliefs and networks. The importance of this theory to this study is the fact that most citizens of Eritrea migrate to Ethiopia as a result of the happenings in their country and the safeties of those who migrate to Ethiopia have to be protected.

Conceptual review

Concept of Refugees

Defining its object of interest is likely the most persistent undertaking of refugee studies (Turton 2003; Hathaway 2007; Betts 2010). Accounting for history makes it just increasingly troublesome. Article 1 of the Geneva Refugee Convention presents the overwhelming comprehension of who is a refugee today, incorporating criteria in the nation of origin and the need of being outside that nation. Betts (2013) on his part point to other important reasons for forced displacement, for example, wars, clashes and economic hardship are reasons that were pertinent right from history. Others question the need of having crossed an international border (Shaknove, 1985), which is a problematic criterion in a historical context likewise, when territorial borders were poorly characterized, not controlled or did not exist by any means. Since the refugee classification relies upon historical conditions of political and social organization, studying refugee history consistently and centuries at that point requires an intelligent and predictable conception of what the object and area of research are. Alternative scholarly definitions frequently point to the refugees changing relationship with states, losing and regaining protection (Shaknove 1985; Gibney 2004). Be that as it may, this requires the presence of current nation states with citizenship and political rights. Arendt (1994) Inspired by old Athens absence of a state, stressed rather political communities that could offer protection and rights. Turning refugee definitions on their head (or rather on their feet), refugee history, at that point, is not predicated on a particularly characterized group of individuals that has not coherently existed since history in any case. Rather, refugee history examines how groups and political organizations offered non-transient security to non-members. Along these lines, refugee

history in another way round examines how societies sorted out and negotiated political belonging and rights through the classification of the refugee. This included refugees themselves who had a functioning impact as they continued looking for protection in forming and changing historical political communities (Gatrell and Lachenicht, 2013). Vitally, we can talk about and think about refugees throughout history because, in contrast to ‘forced migrants’, they are not characterized by reasons of displacement, yet reflect historical improvements of political belonging, rights and protection.

Concept of protection

This shift of point of view on refugees, from stressing displacement to rights, requires likewise reexamining the classification of protection. Today, refugee protection is essentially non-refoulement and, much of the time, likewise the privilege to get to a territory in any case (Heather, 2007). Be that as it may, on the off chance that we consider past societies that are not territorially organized, protection is the consideration into the legal system of a political community by extending a specific status of rights. So also, philanthropy offers protection of human rights without regard to territory in the context of the global legal system. In modern states, nonetheless, the legitimate framework and the privileges of refugee protection are subject to sovereign power that is ostensibly attached to territory, accentuating questions of borders, access and leave to remain (Manasek and Oltmer). Hence, refugee protection concerns a set of rights that are specific of a recorded period and its political and legal system. In ancient Athens, displaced people were exempt from the foreigners’ tax and got lawful rights like those of residents. Today, the Geneva Convention details various social and political rights that must be afforded to refugees, while philanthropy is aimed at protecting the human rights of refugees. Refugee protection is consideration in a political community, a few times with restricted rights or delayed access to full participation, to remedy loss of protection somewhere else. The apparent or contended reasons for displacement that qualify for refugee status incorporate instances like loss of safety or certain rights, norms and organization of the political community however fundamental reasons might be political or economic interests (Gray, Lachenicht, Manasek and Oltmer). Subsequently, refugee protection is characteristic of a historical period and society while being negotiated and changed after some time alongside social and political conflicts and developments (Gray, Lachenicht, Orchard, Oltmer and Glasman). The history of refugee protection is a history of political organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Given, the problem of the paper, this paper adopted the Ex Post Facto (After the Fact) research design. Materials for this paper was sourced through secondary sources of data which included here are textbooks, journal articles, newspapers, magazines, official documents from the government and internet materials, among others. Content analysis was used to analyse data so generated. This is with a view to identify logical sequence of data as well as trends.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Factors that have made Eritrean citizen to migrate to Ethiopia

Identity-based characteristics of the Eritrean population

Eritrea has three authority dialects (Tigrinya, Arabic and English) and a few non-official dialects, including Tigre, Kunama and Afar. The nation has nine recognized ethnic groups, with an uneven populace weighting: Tigrinya (55 %), Tigre (30 %), Saho (4 %), Kunama (2 %), Rashaida (2 %) and Bilen (2 %), with the rest of the 5 % made up of Beni Amer, Afar, Nera and others (CIA, 2015). Huge numbers of these ethnic groups span borders with Ethiopia and Sudan and have truly been in rivalry with neighboring communities for political power and natural assets (Bassi, 2014; Donham and James, 1986). In spite of the fact that the Eritrean government has tried to advance an overwhelming nationalistic character, peoples still identify unequivocally with religious and ethnic identities. The geographic and climatic separation between Eritrea's highlands and swamps is regularly used to classify the populaces inhabiting those areas. Highlanders are customarily Tigrinya-speaking Coptic Christians. The Tigrinya have generally vied for political power in the territory with the Amhara (Bassi, 2014; Donham and James, 1986). Until today, the Tigrinya constitute the prevailing political and cultural group inside Eritrea, and members from different groups, most outstandingly the Kunama and the Afar, have complained of being marginalized and victimized (FCO, 2015). The lowlanders are overwhelmingly Muslim migrant pastoralists from various ethnic groups, with the exemptions of the Kunama and Bilen groups, which are agriculturalists and frequently non-Coptic Christians.

Discrimination towards minorities

Public discourses celebrate the rich cultural legacy of various Eritrean minorities, yet this has not forestalled ethnic oppression happening, particularly on account of the Kunama and the Afar. The Kunama have encountered oppression from neighboring communities since pre-colonial times (Longrigg, 1945; Naty, 2002; Pollera, 1935). Since the Ethiopia–Eritrea border crisis, their circumstance has again deteriorated (Tronvoll, 2009). The Kunama resistance fronts (for example the Democratic Movement for the Liberation of the Eritrean Kunama) were blamed for supporting the Ethiopian armed force and administering the captured territories from 1999 to 2000, and of going with the Ethiopian troops when they fled. This brought about summed up retaliations by government forces once the war finished. Those from the Kunama who fled in 2000 were among the first Eritrean displaced people in Ethiopia and establish the main populace in Shimelba refugee camp. A few reports (Human Rights Watch, 2015; ILO and ACHPR, 2009) record that the Kunama keep on leaving Eritrea, to escape national service and as a result of on-going area confiscation by the Eritrean government. Nonetheless, discrimination towards the Kunama is likewise established in more extensive societal dispositions that view them as uncivilized and inferior (ILO and ACHPR, 2009). Political organizations, writers and humanitarian agencies have recorded mistreatment towards individuals from the Afar ethnic group. Research on this issue is uncommon, however recounted reports propose the Afar face

specific ethnic and cultural abuse in Eritrea (Connell, 2015). This discrimination may likewise be associated with Afar secessionist political yearnings (EASE, 2014).

State role in the marginalization of minorities

The Eritrean government visualizes Sawa Defense Training Center as an apparatus of social engineering for nation building, through inspiring prominent faithfulness to the country than pre-existing familial, community or religious connections (Healy, 2007). Its accomplishment in such manner is difficult to measure. Land reform policies have fortified conventional patterns of discrimination and marginalization. They are contended to have had a 'lopsided effect on pastoralists, for example, the Afar and Kunama minorities and have been 'utilized as a methods by authorities to harass and rebuff apparent foes, specifically individuals from unapproved religions, rivals and relatives of individuals who fled the nation (UN COI, 2015). There is as of now little proof of specific minority groups encountering intensifying marginalization, in spite of the fact that the results of systematic exclusion may turn out to be progressively obvious after some time. State interventions, for example, land seizure and national service, disturb conventional jobs and may progressively affect minorities and their capacity to get by in a challenging environment that is forecast to intensify because of climate change. This may bring about increased migration towards neighboring nations. It ought to likewise be viewed as that the Kunama and Afar ethnic groups live across the Ethiopian border and that, on account of the Afar, migration has customarily represented a way to adapt to climatic and political afflictions (Yasin, 2008). This suggests that the Afar may dynamically turn to migration as a strategy to go around interruptions of the Eritrean state in their conventional ways of life. Kibreab (1987) noted similar patterns during the 1960s, with lowlanders in western Eritrea crossing the border with no trouble because of cross-border ethnic affiliations.

Religious and gender issues

There is restricted freedom of religion in Eritrea, with people allowed to have a place with one of four beliefs: Orthodox Christianity, Roman Catholicism, Lutheranism as practiced by the Evangelical Church of Eritrea and Islam (Freedom House, 2015). People practicing different beliefs, specifically Jehovah's witnesses and those belonging to Pentecostal or Evangelical churches have encountered discrimination, provocation, torment and imprisonment by the administration (Mekonnen and van Reisen, 2013). Same-sex sexual relations are generally condemned in Eritrean culture and face more awful criminal sentences in Eritrea than pedophilia, and Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender (LGBT) people face discrimination at a social and legitimate level. There is no enactment to prevent this, and the Eritrean government has voiced 'that they do not expect to change this circumstance (FCO, 2015). The Eritrean government has, since the freedom war, tried to advance uniformity between the genders, including through legal protection. Be that as it may, ladies still face difficulties because of cultural attitudes and absence of economic opportunities, particularly for female guerrilla fighters, who attempted to reintegrate after their demobilization (Bernal, 2006; Dore, 2002). Female genital cutting (FGC) remains

worrisome. The Eritrean government has launched a few information campaigns demoralizing these practices and in 2007 totally prohibited Female Genital Mutilation (FGM), commanding serious punishments for those performing such mutilations. In any case, it is accounted for that 83% of Eritrean ladies had been mutilated and these practices are profoundly rooted in cultural and religious convictions (UNICEF, 2013). FGM remains common in every single ethnic group, in spite of the fact that the kind and seriousness of the mutilation differs extraordinarily between ethnic groups, with the Hidareb having the most elevated level of the most drastic kind of FGM.

Measures taken by the Ethiopian government to protect Eritrean refugees

The Ethiopia government refugee affairs are within the remit of the National Intelligence and Security Service (NISS) under the Ministry of Federal Affairs. By and by, this obligation falls to the Administration for Refugee and Returnee Affairs (ARRA), a semi-self-governing body with duty regarding the implementation of all policies relating to refugees and returnees. As indicated by a 2013 assessment of UNHCR's response, ARRA is both an implementing partner for most sectorial exercises and a government body that monitors, manages and approves partners to work. In addition, through its arrangement in the National Intelligence and Security Service and with its commitment in border areas, ARRA has a further double job of a security agency verses a service provision agency. The 2013 assessment of UNHCR likewise noticed that ARRA kept tight control over its job as implementing partner, restricting the opening up of humanitarian space to international agencies. Ethiopia is involved in the 1951 UN Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, however holds formal reservations in regards to displaced people's entitlement to work and primary education. Ethiopia's national legitimate structure, the Refugee Proclamation of 2004, allowed refugees a few rights however with limitations on rights of movement and residence and the right to work. Until 2009, Ethiopia enforced a strict policy of place to stay for all refugees. Beginning in 2010, be that as it may, the nation started executing an "out-of-camp policy" enabling Eritrean displaced people to live outside camps provided they can bolster themselves financially or have the help of relatives officially living in non-camp zones. In 2015, somewhere in the range of 8 000 Eritrean refugees lived in Addis Ababa under the out-of-camp policy and a few hundred lived in different urban communities. At the September 2016 Refugee Summit, the Ethiopian government promised to loosen up its place to stay policy for all displaced people, raising the number of out-of-camp recipients to 10% of the refugee populace. Displaced people in Ethiopia, regardless of whether they live in camps or in urban communities, cannot participate in formal employment and have generally had restricted access to land for agrarian production. Ethiopian law limits access to work licenses for outsiders, and, practically speaking, work licenses are not granted to refugees and asylum seekers, forestalling their entrance to the formal market. As indicated by a 2015 US assessment, the administration of Ethiopia pursues a strict policy of possibly allowing work licenses to outsiders when there are no qualified nationals accessible to do practically identical work. These permits are once in a while issued to refugees due both to absence of qualified staff and discrimination against the refugee populaces. Also, refugees cannot acquire business licenses and it is practically incomprehensible

for refugees to build up their own enterprises. Most refugees have been limited to casual jobs and they need full legal protection. Work in the informal sector has additionally been liable to government regulation, and in refugee camps, government authorities have strict regulations about the kind of casual work in which refugees can have interest in.

Moreover, refugees are commonly not permitted to claim land in Ethiopia. A few reports additionally show that the failure to get to formal business may expose refugees to labour market exploitation with instances of refugees working for small wages. A 2011 impact assessment commissioned by the UNHCR and World Food Program (WFP) noticed the seriously constrained salary generating opportunities accessible for refugees. The principle pay generating opportunities for refugees was work as day laborers. This assessment additionally found that refugee families needed access to land for cultivating and grazing, and that confinement on the movement of refugees implied they had few chances for agrarian production. In any case, families that got settlements were significantly better off. The assessment said benefactors had given over USD 100 million to UNHCR and WFP “to give refugees adequate food and non-food items, while livelihood programming had attracted just an extremely little proportion of donor assistance. While WFP was giving food aid to refugee camps, notwithstanding, refugees were excluded in WFP programmers promoting sustainable livelihoods, profitable wellbeing nets and school feeding programmers that were profiting rural communities in areas encompassing the camps. The assessment noticed that UNHCR needed funding to advance refugee independence and that the long term distribution of full food rations, joined with the constrained economic opportunities for refugees, “created a reliance syndrome” and kept refugees from accomplishing confidence. Subsequently Somali displaced people had been available for a long time in camps yet lacked financial opportunity to seek after employment opportunities, while simultaneously “significant donors had not energetically campaigned for policy changes that may expand refugees’ economic rights, and in this manner strong solutions”.

In spite of its official policies restricting refugees' entitlement to work in both the formal and informal sectors, as noted above, the administration has permitted some particular initiatives that aim to empower refugees to discover salary generating activities in the informal sector. There are various instances of such activities lately to advance independent work and self-reliance. Between 2012 and 2014, for example, the International Labor Organization (ILO) partnered with UNHCR and the Administration for Refugee and Returnee Affairs (ARRA) to actualize a project advancing wage employment and self-employment within refugee camps and the surrounding host communities in the Dollo Ado territory of southeastern Ethiopia. By facilitating economic exchange and cooperation among hosts and refugees, the venture increased family pay and added to improving social cohesion. UNHCR, local authorities and the IKEA Foundation united forces in 2012-14 in another venture in a same region in which local authorities dispensed 1000 hectares of land for agricultural activity and, UNHCR put resources into water system and infrastructure with the help of the IKEA Foundation. The objective of this

task was to increase household salary for 50 000 refugees and individuals of the host community. On 20 September 2016, at the Leaders' Summit on Refugees, Ethiopia promised to make accessible 10 000 hectares of irrigable land within the limits of the national laws of Ethiopia to permit 20 000 displaced person and host community households (100 000 individuals) to take part in crop production by encouraging irrigation plans, subject to the accessibility of external financial help. These new activities show positive advancement since refugees in the Dollo Ado camp had not had numerous livelihood opportunities previously. The camp encountered a huge influx of Somali refugees following extreme dry seasons in the Horn of Africa in mid-2011. The 2013 assessment of the UNHCR response noticed that refugees there had "no business opportunities and depleted resources" when they came. This prompted a reliance on food aid, with refugees compelled to sell food aid as a course of money to meet other fundamental needs. The circumstance was especially concerning, the assessment included, since a considerable lot of the refugees have come needing life-sparing help and with abnormal levels of lack of healthy sustenance. The inability to give money or other livelihood support consequently heightened the level of malnutrition.

As the Horn of Africa region is inclined to food insecurity, a significant lesson to be drawn is that giving food aid to refugees in camps in Ethiopia is not adequate, especially in the event that they need to sell a portion of their food rations to help their other essential needs. The assessment noticed lack of healthy sustenance rates "in the set up camps hovered around 33% while in the new arrivals it was almost 50%. Death rates were far above emergency thresholds". There is proof of projects in different camps that emphasis on self-reliance. In the Jijiga territory, where there are three camps housing almost 40 000 Somali refugees, UNHCR likewise engages refugees and host communities in self-reliance activities under its Development Assistance for Refugees venture. International non-governmental organizations (INGOs) are additionally implementing loans and training programs in refugee camps near the border with Eritrea intending to give money to build up micro-enterprises, furnish members with professional abilities in a specific sector (for example, computing or tailoring), as well as give essential instructive aptitudes. While the circumstance is changing and some advancement has been seen on the ground, constrained strategic thinking to longer-term sustainable programming and not many assets devoted to employments and self-reliance were highlighted in the UNHCR response to the influx of enormous numbers of South Sudanese refugees in Ethiopia. A 2015 assessment of US refugees activities in Ethiopia additionally highlighted the absence of livelihood programming and backing for refugee in certain camps. With such an absence of opportunities of livelihood, refugees stay unfit to meet their essential needs and depend completely upon aid and assistance. When they exist, job and professional training programmers have by and large empowered refugees to "increase salary and food security, improve their self-esteem and confidence" and to improve instruction, learn new abilities that they can use in the wake of returning home, in resettlement, and to a restricted degree while still living in the camps.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that there are factors that have made Eritreans to migrate to Ethiopia which includes; Identity-based characteristics of the Eritrean population, discrimination towards minorities, State role in the marginalization of minorities and religious and gender issues. The study further concluded that the Ethiopian government has taken steps to protect the refugees that came from Eritrea such as setting up of the refugees affairs which is within the remit of the National Intelligent and Security Service (NISS). The study also concluded that despite the measures taken by the by the Ethiopian government to protect refugees coming from Eritrea, it has not done enough as regards getting formal employment and limited access to land for agriculture among others.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings the study recommended the following.

- 1) Eritrea refugees in Ethiopia must be genuinely incorporated into meetings at national and international levels about responses and frameworks that will influence them, including plans for national-level exhaustive refugees response framework execution. Refugee protection including their fundamental human rights must be at the core of the global compact on refugees.
- 2) Ethiopia government must set up plans that prioritize the material needs of refugees as well as progressively fundamental human needs to carry on with a noble life, to have the conditions empowering them to satisfy their yearnings, and the legitimate, social and psychological assistance expected to realize those.
- 3) The international community must re-attest and maintain the essential humankind and rights of refugees; all commitments and interventions set up under the comprehensive refugees response structure must have as their core value regard for the humanity of every individual refugee.

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